

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR FORMING SPORTS MOTIVATION

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***Annotation.** The essence and content of sports motivation and the peculiarities of its relationship with the personality traits of athletes have been determined on the basis of a theoretical analysis of scientific and methodological literature. The pedagogical conditions of the formation of sports motivation of volleyball players of 15-16 years old were revealed.*

***Key words:** motive, sports motivation, sports activity, personality traits, level of aspirations.*

Motivation occupies a leading place in the structure of the personality, permeating all its structural formations: personality orientation, character, emotions, abilities, mental processes. Motivation of behavior is impossible outside the emotional sphere [1]. Emotions orient a person, indicating the significance of the environment for a person, the degree of their importance, their modality. The degree of significance indicates the permissible level of material and functional-energy costs necessary for the implementation of the impulses.

In the psychological literature, it is proposed to distinguish between the concepts of motive and motivation. Motives are understood as: 1) subjective dynamic forces (tendencies) aimed at ridding a person of oppressive states of tension; 2) subjective images of objects that satisfy the corresponding needs, and give the activity directed at them a personal meaning; 3) special fixed installations that determine the readiness for activity in appropriate conditions and in a certain direction; 4) stable evaluative dispositions.

Motivation is considered as a mental state that is formed as a result of a person's correlation of his needs and capabilities with the specifics of a specific activity and serves as the basis for setting and implementing its goals.

The specificity of sports motivation is due to the qualitative originality of the subject of sports activity. R.A. Piloyan [1] defines sports motivation as "a special state of an athlete's personality, which is formed as a result of his / her correlation of his abilities and capabilities with the subject of sports activity, which serves as the basis for setting and implementing goals aimed at achieving the maximum possible sports result at the moment."

Sports activity is characterized by such psychological characteristics as an orientation towards the ultimate level of achievement and high emotional stress associated with the subjective significance of the results of activity, the severity of rivalry, and the publicity of performances in competitions. In the duration and effectiveness of sports, a significant role belongs to the motivational sphere of the individual [2].

The motives for playing sports of the highest achievements include, according to A.V. Rodionov [3], the need for extreme physical efforts, experiencing a state of strong mental tension, overcoming an opponent, testing one's own physical and mental capabilities.

The priority of motives, the peculiarities of the structure of motives are influenced by the specificity of the kind of sport, the level of sports achievements, age, gender, sports experience of an athlete, as well as self-assessment of their personal qualities [4].

Sports psychologists propose to distinguish between sports motives and sports motivation. In particular, V.K. Safonov identifies two levels of sports motivation:

1. General motivation. Its formation is the task of the entire educational process. A prerequisite for this is the setting and consolidation of a far-backed goal in the mind of an athlete.

2. The motivation of an athlete at a given training session, at a specific stage of training, which, refracted through general motivation, is actualized through the awareness of the tasks of this stage of training and self-assessment of his state, functional capabilities.

The development and functioning of sports motivation presupposes the need for a high level of development of a number of personality traits: 1) a positive attitude to sports and overcoming the difficulties of sports activity [5]; 2) emotional and volitional qualities - determination, decisiveness, perseverance, self-confidence, self-control, resourcefulness, emotional stability [6]; 3) a sense of collectivism and its manifestations [7].

Sports motivation is defined as the current state of the athlete's personality, which serves as the basis for setting and implementing goals aimed at achieving the maximum possible sports result at the moment. It was revealed that, on the one hand, motivation affects the nature of training activity and directly on the competitive result, on the other hand, an increase in the effectiveness of competitive activity enhances sports motivation.

E.G. Babushkin [7] proposes to distinguish training and competitive motivation in the structure of sports motivation. In turn, there are two components in competitive motivation: motivation to achieve success and motivation to avoid failure [8, 9].

Athletes with dominant motivation for achieving success are distinguished by the desire to win, the ability to "fight to the end", positive emotions, the tendency to dominate, the desire to take risks, insensitivity to threat, low anxiety, an attacking style of fighting, high intensity of effort and the effectiveness of behavior in extreme situations.

It was revealed that the motivation for achieving success affects the purpose and content of the action, the intensity of the effort and behavior in extreme situations. B.I. Stepansky [9] found that with the dominance of achievement

motivation, the performance is determined by the current level of activity regulation, that is, by its psychophysiological characteristics. If the motivation for avoiding failure prevails at any level of activity regulation, its effectiveness will be low.

The manifestation of sports motivation depends on the characteristics of athletes' self-esteem of their personal qualities. According to the research results of A.V. Shabolta, the significant parameters of self-esteem, regardless of the sport and gender of athletes, are self-confidence, satisfaction with sports results, authority, and health. In particular, it was revealed that self-confidence is closely related to sports achievements, the motive for achieving success and the emotionality of sports activity.

In a number of works, the ratio of motives and goals of sports activity was considered. G. D. Gorbunov writes that the process of subjective goal-setting and the motivational sphere of an athlete are closely related, and the decisive role in this is assigned to self-affirmation. The development of such a motive must be considered in connection with the formation of an athlete's value system, which should be based on a critical assessment of personal behavior and achievements. An athlete's critical attitude to his behavior is impossible without self-esteem and identification with generally accepted social and social norms.

The athlete's personal values determine his level of claims to himself and to his achievement.

An important prerequisite for the implementation of the regulatory function of the goal is its subjective acceptance by the athlete. The more clearly the athlete realizes the tasks facing him, the deeper he understands and experiences the importance and social significance of solving these problems, the more intense the urge to resolve them. The more difficult and serious the goal, the more efforts are made by athletes [10]. The difficulty of the goal chosen by the athlete characterizes the level of her aspirations in the field of sports activity. The level of an athlete's aspirations must correspond to his capabilities [11].

As stress increases, individuals with a strong nervous system overestimate the level of aspirations, while those with a weak nervous system underestimate it. E.P. Ilyin [12] gives signs of the behavior of athletes with high and low levels of claims. The former overestimate their capabilities, claim high marks from others and experience bad luck. Athletes with a low level of aspirations underestimate themselves, do not strive to rise above the achieved level, are reluctant to take on difficult tasks, and are afraid of failure. The athlete's level of aspirations can be influenced by past successes and failures, the ability to realistically assess the current situation, the ability to foresee the course and result of an action. The volitional activity of an athlete, his desire for the intended goal, the higher, the more important the motive and the higher the level of aspirations (the more difficult the goal).

In general, the research results indicate a close relationship between motivational attitudes, the level of aspirations, self-esteem, and personality traits.

Summarizing the research results of domestic and foreign researchers, we can conclude that they distinguish the following motives associated with the process of sports activity: the need for physical activity; aesthetic enjoyment; the desire for competition; active rest and entertainment; the need for extreme physical effort; striving for a state of stress and overcoming it.

Along with this, the authors highlight the motives associated with the results of sports activity: testing their own physical and mental capabilities; the desire to become healthy, strong, physically, to achieve a beautiful physique, to improve physical abilities; personality formation: the desire to temper the will, to become courageous and persistent; raising social status, social self-affirmation; achieving success in sports; orientation to the possible negative consequences of success; desire for contacts in a sports team; material needs, social conditions; preparation for professional activity; accumulation of special knowledge and skills, knowledge about their opponents; lack of pain and psychogenic influences; desire to visit competitions in other cities of the country and, especially abroad; desire to become

a coach in the future; ethical motives: awareness of the importance of sports activities, the desire to glorify their country, the desire for sports improvement for a successful performance for a sports team.

The development of motivation for sports activity is conditioned by the interaction of internal and external factors that change their significance during sports activity. As internal factors for the development of motivation, the following are distinguished: age, the inclinations of motor abilities and a propensity for activities with a certain content. The role of external factors is played by the social environment, which reflects both the traditional social and moral norms inherent in society and the attitude towards the athlete's personality.

The development of internal and external factors is carried out through their interaction in the course of sports activities. As a result of the development of internal factors, the goals and objectives of sports are formed, which are adequate, on the one hand, to personally significant needs, on the other hand, to the possibilities and characteristics of the activity being performed. The development of external factors is manifested mainly in the improvement of the organization of the educational training process (training conditions, organization and methodology of training, high emotionality of training sessions) and competitive activity.

For the development of motivation, the high satisfaction of athletes with the results of sports activity, taking into account their compliance with its goals and objectives (as a result of the effective interaction of internal and external factors), is of decisive importance, information about which is promptly received by the athlete from the coach through the feedback channels.

The ultimate goal of psychological training is the formation and improvement of the sports motivation of the individual through the daily (in the process of each training session and competition) stabilization of the athlete's attitudes to the process and results of sports activities, to the coach and teammates, to himself. Psychological training aimed at the formation of sports motivation is carried out in unity with other

types of sports training. Therefore, all physical exercises and rehabilitation measures performed by athletes should be considered in conjunction not only with their physical states, but also with the mental states of those involved in this being actualized.

In the literature, such questions as: the features of the competitive and training motivation of volleyball in adolescence have not been reflected; the relationship of sports motivation, self-assessment of sports capabilities and volitional qualities; management of the formation of sports motivation; the relationship of sports motivation with the personality traits of an athlete and the level of their sports readiness. This determined the relevance of our study.

Our long-term research on this problem with volleyball players 15-16 years old allowed us to come to the following conclusion.

Formation of the relationship underlying sports motivation is carried out through the psychological mechanisms "bottom up" and "top down".

The action of the mechanism "from the bottom up" is provided through the directed creation of special external conditions in the process of extra-training, educational-training and competitive activity (for example, situations of achieving success, the need to make a timely decision in a personally significant and uncertain situation, etc.), which objectively require athletes to actualize the formed motives and volitional qualities, and lead to an independent decision on the implementation of related actions.

Simultaneously with the setting in specially organized external conditions of sports activity, the trainer, through the use of methods of suggestion and persuasion, is brought to the consciousness and understanding of athletes, what kind of orientation and emotional coloring should be the attitude to these conditions, under which high efficiency of sports activity is achieved (the action of the mechanism "from top to bottom ").

Theoretical analysis and generalization of literary data made it possible to single out a number of pedagogical conditions, the implementation of which in the process of sports training through psychological mechanisms "from bottom to top" and "from top to bottom" should ensure, according to our assumption, the emergence, functioning and development of volleyball players' attitudes towards the goal of sports, sports success, their capabilities, educational training and competitive activities, to the team and the coach.

Stabilization of these relations leads to the formation of the motives of going in for sports, volitional qualities, the ability to subjective control and self-government, which subsequently become the personal basis of internally organized sports motivation.

At the same time, in our opinion, it is necessary to observe the following pedagogical conditions that we have highlighted:

- formation of favorable attitudes towards the goal of playing sports;
- formation of favorable attitudes towards sporting success;
- the formation of favorable attitudes towards their capabilities;
- formation of favorable attitudes towards training and competitive activities;
- formation of favorable relations to the team and the coach.

Summarizing the results of the study, we can conclude that with the practical implementation of the pedagogical conditions we have identified in the educational and training process of volleyball players aged 15-16, the following is observed:

- 1) accelerating the pace of development of volitional qualities of purposefulness, perseverance and perseverance;
- 2) weakening the importance of the motive of emotional pleasure and increasing the importance of the motives for achieving success, social and physical self-affirmation;
- 3) strengthening of sports motivation and competitive motivation;

4) increasing the level of subjective control and the ability to self-govern communication, behavior and activities.

To manage the formation of sports motivation, it is necessary to create pedagogical conditions for the emergence, functioning and stabilization of these relations by means of psychological mechanisms “from bottom to top” and “from top to bottom”.

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